

Spectroscopic investigation on Red soil samples from Thiruvannamalai District, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract—*In this study, the eight different Red soil samples collected in Thiruvannamalai district is subjected to physic-chemical and mineralogical characterizations. FT-IR spectroscopic technique is applied to soil samples to identify the constituent minerals. From the infrared spectrum, the minerals are identified from the absorption frequencies of peaks with the help of available literature. The minerals such as quartz and clay minerals like kaolinite and montmorillonite are majorly present in the samples and also feldspar minerals (orthoclase, microcline, and albite) and carbonate minerals (aragonite and calcite) and organic carbon are identified. Few minerals like chlorite, gypsum, goethite, ilmenite, dolomite, magnetite, garnet, hornblende, kyanite, zircon and magnesiohornblende are identified only in XRD analysis. The performed analyses provided useful information about the mineralogical composition of the red soil samples. FT-IR spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction technique seems to be useful method for the mineral analysis of red soil samples.*

Keywords- Red soil; Mineral analysis; FT-IR; XRD

I. INTRODUCTION

Soil is made up of a combination of mineral, organic substances air and water. However, it is divided into categories based on the size of the mineral particles. Sand, silt, and clay are the three basic structural groups. Sand particles are largest in comparatively both the particles silt and clay. The particle size of sand particles varies from 2.0 mm to 0.05 mm, silt particles have 0.05 mm to 0.02 mm and clay particles have less than 0.02 mm. The soil plays a vital function in supporting human activities and serving as an important substrate for growing plants on the planet. The soil is fertile and holds the necessary nutrients needed to support plants growth for human and animal needs such as food and clothing [1]. As a protection for plant roots and a container that holds water for essential moisture, the soil where the plants are rooted is provides a suitable space. Agricultural terrestrial areas are rich in porous loamy soils (fine clay soils) which are made of organic matter that retains water and provides nutrients to the crop. The soils are not only used for agricultural purpose is also used in many fields like medicine, cosmetics, pottery and building material especially clay materials play a vital role in ceramics industries [2].

The soil varies from one place to another, even from the backyard of a building to another building's backyard. They differ in where and how they formed. Five key factors that involved in creating various types of soils such as climate, organisms, landscape, parent material and time. Climate is involved in soil formation through temperature and moisture. Warmth and humidity affect the velocity of chemical reactions, which helps control how quickly rocks weather and dead creatures disintegrate. The soil grows fast in hot, humid climates slow in cold or dries [3].

The study of soil minerals is very important because it is necessary to ensure that the minerals required for plant growth are present in the soil. The qualitative and quantitative determination of clay minerals present in soil samples by using Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) is an important and efficient technique for the determination of minerals in soils [4, 5]. The XRD techniques are best for mineral identification as it is quick, cheap and time-saving. The powder x-ray diffraction method also gives information on minerals in the soil or sediment samples [6, 7]. Both the techniques XRD and FT-IR are used to identifying the minor and major constituents of mineral in the soil samples.

II. STUDY AREA

Eight locations in the district Thiruvannamalai were chosen for this investigation, i.e., Na. Pudhooor, Kattumalaiyanoor, Sooriyanthangal, Udhayasooriyapuram, Arumbakkam, Kalingaleri, Konalur and Velanandhal. Having North latitude ($12^{\circ} 9'30.13''$) to ($12^{\circ}10'27.98''$) and East longitude ($79^{\circ} 9'25.69''$) to ($79^{\circ} 8'49.77''$) respectively. The district Thiruvannamalai lies between northeastern parts of the Tamil Nadu state in India. The district covers at 6,191 km² and the population of 2,604,569. It has an abundance of natural resources and environmental riches with forest in western part. Easter part of the area covers plain region [8]. Rice, wheat, paddy, groundnut and sugarcane crops are cultivating and processing are the major businesses in Thiruvannamalai district and its surrounding villages. This study was conducted just between Na. Pudhooor to Velanandhal, where many densely agricultural fields are being established. The soils in our study area are mainly contaminated by the various types of pollutions like dust, usage of untreated wastewater for irrigation, using of pesticides and fertilizers, domestic e-waste, high antibiotic, antimicrobial-resistant bacteria and heavy metal content.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Sample Collection

In this investigation, red soil samples are collected from 8 different locations in Na. Pudhooor to Velanandhal situated in Thiruvannamalai, Tamil Nadu, India. The sample locations are close to populated agriculture fields. The geographical coordinates of their respective locations is shown in table 1.

Table 1: Geo-graphical coordinates of sampling points of red soils from Thiruvannamalai

Sample Location	Sample ID	Latitude	Longitude
Na. Pudhooor	RS-1	$12^{\circ}10'7.85''N$	$79^{\circ}10'12.78''E$
Kattumalaiyanoor	RS-2	$12^{\circ}11'3.14''N$	$79^{\circ} 9'56.71''E$
Sooriyanthangal	RS-3	$12^{\circ}10'58.62''N$	$79^{\circ} 9'30.49''E$
Udhayasooriyapuram	RS-4	$12^{\circ}11'4.64''N$	$79^{\circ} 8'47.79''E$
Arumbakkam	RS-5	$12^{\circ}11'9.29''N$	$79^{\circ} 8'47.03''E$
Kalingaleri	RS-6	$12^{\circ}11'53.43''N$	$79^{\circ} 9'1.71''E$
Konalur	RS-7	$12^{\circ}10'21.11''N$	$79^{\circ} 9'14.72''E$
Velanandhal	RS-8	$12^{\circ}10'33.30''N$	$79^{\circ} 8'27.49''E$

Eight different red soils samples were collected from eight different locations in the sampling area. At all the sampling sites, soil samples were collected from upper surface layer with the depth is about 5-10 cm [9, 10]. Five top surface of soil samples were collected at the four corners and the center of a 1 m² of each point. The soils were then mixed up to make the amount of around 2 kg was taken using a quartile method from each point. The same procedure was followed in each site. These soil samples were collected during April, 2021. This time period was also the dry season in Thiruvannamalai with the outdoor temperature of about 30-40 °C [11]. All the samples were sealed in polythene carry bags and it was properly catalogued and marked according to the location site. Then all samples were carefully transported to laboratory for preparation and analysis.

B. Sample preparation

After collection of soil samples, pieces of stones and organic materials were removed. The soil samples were dried in room temperature about 24 hours at laboratory. Then the soil samples were dried in hot air oven at the temperature of 80 °C for the duration (3-4 hrs) in order to remove the moisture and make it constant weight. The soil samples were crushed with agate mortar and pestle to make fine powdered and sieve in mesh 63 micron with American Standard Test Sieve Series (ASTM) [12]. Their respective net weight about 5-10 g of sieved soil samples were measured with a highly sensitive balance and packed into the zip lock cover. At the end of this procedure the prepared soil samples for the further characterization of (FT-IR) Spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction (XRD).

C. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) analysis

The major and minor minerals are determined by using the Fourier Transform Infrared technique (FT-IR). FT-IR is a crucial tool for assessing the presence of clay minerals in soil and sediment samples [13]. In this

process, the KBr pressed pellet method was used to identify the mineral constituents present in the soil samples. Before preparing the pellet the Potassium Bromide (KBr) was dried at 120 °C for 6 to 12 hours in oven to remove the moisture and grounded as a fine powder. The powdered KBr of 40 mg and mixed with the powdered soil samples of 2 mg in the ratio of 1:20 using pestle and mortar [14]. This mixture was pressed 5 tons per minute to make the disc. This process was repeated several times to prepare pellets for each soil sample collected from the sample area. Infrared spectrum from the midline region of 400 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹ was recorded for each sample using this technique.

D. X-ray Diffraction Analysis (XRD)

In this work, a powder X-ray diffractometer was used for mineralogical analysis of soil samples. It consists of several different parts including the cathode ray tube, sample holder and detector [15]. X-ray diffractometer having a curved graphite crystal diffracted monochromator, with a source of CuK α radiation [16]. By scanning the samples through a range of 2 θ angles between 10 to 80° with a counting time of 5 minutes was conducted.

The preparation of samples for x-ray powder diffraction analysis is particularly so for quantitative analysis of soils and it is an important aspect of soil mineralogical analysis [17]. Initially, 100 mg of fine, homogeneous and well-grounded soil samples with the grain size 63 μ m was taken for accurate x-ray diffraction intensities to find the minerals present in samples.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Minerals Present in Soil Samples by FT-IR Analysis

By comparing the available literature the minerals are obtained from the FT-IR absorption spectra of the soil samples such as quartz and clay minerals like kaolinite and montmorillonite are majorly present in the samples and also feldspar minerals (orthoclase, microcline, and albite) and carbonate minerals (aragonite and calcite) are present in the samples and it clearly represented in table 2 with figure 1 their respective absorption frequencies.

Table 2: Observed frequencies through FT-IR for red soils

Sample ID	Silicate Minerals	Gibbsite	Feldspar			Clay Minerals			Carbonate Minerals		Organic carbon
	Quartz		Orthoclase	Microcline	Albite	Kaolinite	Montmorilinte	Illite	Calcite	Aragonite	
RS-1	694	997	538, 465	535, 593	787	3620, 3429, 1034, 3701	1639, 1637	-	1437, 1438	-	2925
RS-2	692	1002	647	535	-	3626, 1035, 917, 470, 3700	1637	-	1444, 1437	1457	2922
RS-3	778,692	1001,997	647	535	787	3620, 3429, 1034	1637	-	1438, 1444	-	2922, 2925
RS-4	779,694	998	538, 465	535, 593	787	470, 3700	1637	-	1438	1457	2922
RS-5	779,693	1001	647	593	-	911, 3623, 3702	1639, 1637	1629	1444	-	2922, 2925
RS-6	778,692	1000	538, 465	535	787	913, 3701, 470, 3700	1637	-	1437, 1438	1457	2925
RS-7	778	998	538, 465	593	787	3630, 913, 3701	1637	1636	1444	1457	2922
RS-8	779	1002,998	647	535, 593	-	3626, 1035, 917, 470, 3700	1639, 1637	-	1438, 1444	1457	2922, 2925

Figure 1: shows the FT-IR spectrum of representative red soil samples.

a) *Quartz:*

Quartz (silicate minerals) is a common mineral that is mostly present in the environmental samples. In this FT-IR spectra of these soil samples shows that the quartz are the common mineral of the red soils because it is a widely spreaded mineral of the crust of earth [18]. Quartz also is one of the rock-forming mineral in the earth's crust it will present in the three major rocks (Igneous, Sedimentary and Metamorphic). In this soil sample quartz are present at the absorption band such as, 692 cm^{-1} , 693 cm^{-1} , 779 cm^{-1} , and 788 cm^{-1} . Except the peaks at 692 cm^{-1} and 693 cm^{-1} the observed frequencies of quartz may be assigned as symmetrical bending vibration mode [19].

b) *Feldspar minerals:*

In earth's crust the 60 % of portion is occupied by rock-forming mineral Feldspar because the crust of the earth is made up with the rocks [20]. Feldspar is found in many types of rocks include granite, basalt and other types of crystalline rocks. The absorbed frequencies of the soil samples by the FT-IR technique the observed peaks at 465 cm^{-1} , 538 cm^{-1} , 647 cm^{-1} are referred to as orthoclase mineral. Microcline mineral are present at the peaks values such as, 535 cm^{-1} and 593 cm^{-1} . The observed peak at 787 cm^{-1} is well known as Albite mineral. And these determinations are carried by many researchers at different [21-30].

c) *Clay minerals:*

Clay is an abundant mineral in the soil and sediments samples. Clay minerals include Kaolinite, Montmorillonite, Illite are present in red soil sample. In these samples kaolinite is majorly present minerals in between the band range at 3620 cm^{-1} to 3630 cm^{-1} , 3695 cm^{-1} to 3699 cm^{-1} , 910 cm^{-1} to 920 cm^{-1} , 3700 cm^{-1} to 3701 cm^{-1} and also observed peaks at 3425 cm^{-1} , 3439 cm^{-1} , 1034 cm^{-1} , 1035 cm^{-1} and 470 cm^{-1} . In these peak values 3700 cm^{-1} to 3600 cm^{-1} is shows that the kaolinite is present in the sharp absorption band position. The strong absorption peaks at 3695 cm^{-1} to 3699 cm^{-1} is may be attributed to hydroxyl linkage [20]. These soil spectra show that kaolinite mineral is a majorly present constituent of clay minerals. The absorbed peak value 3620 cm^{-1} is indicating the assigned in O-H stretching of inner hydroxyl [26]. The observed absorption bands at 873 cm^{-1} , 875 cm^{-1} , 1637 cm^{-1} , 1639 cm^{-1} , 1642 cm^{-1} and 3435 cm^{-1} are indicate the presence of Montmorillonite. 1637 cm^{-1} and 1639 cm^{-1} these peaks are indicating the mineral montmorillonite is has O-H absorbed water vibration. And the remaining peak are represents that presence of Illite at 1635 cm^{-1} .

d) *Carbonate minerals:*

In this soil sample carbonate minerals, it include calcite, Aragonite, dolomite, and siderite which are the anion $(\text{CO}_3)^{2-}$ are present in trace amount and it is clearly shown in the absorbed peaks at 1437 cm^{-1} , 1438 cm^{-1} and 1444 cm^{-1} . The peak at 1457 cm^{-1} is known as Aragonite (born calcium carbonate) mineral remaining peaks are indicating the presence of calcite mineral in the soil sample.

e) *Organic carbon:*

The organic carbon is present in these soil samples in a very trace amount. The absorption bands at 2922cm^{-1} and 2925cm^{-1} are indicating the presence of the organic component in the soil samples [31]. And these bands are represented contamination of C-H absorption.

B. *X-ray diffraction analysis*

The powdered soil samples were analyzed for general mineralogical studies to confirm the minerals presented in samples by using X-ray diffraction (XRD) instrument with fixing of 2θ position values in between 2θ values $0-80^\circ$ in x-axis and intensity (cps) in y-axis. The diffraction spectrum of the soil samples RS1 and RS2 are shown in figure 2a and 2b. 2θ values are taken from the obtained XRD peaks and relative d-spacing values are identified through [32] of all the soil samples. In this technique, minerals are identified by comparing 2θ values with d-spacing values (it allows identification of the mineral because each mineral has a set of unique d-spacing) from JCPDS file [33].

Figure 2(a): XRD spectrum of Red soil sample – RS1

Figure 2(b): XRD spectrum of Red soil sample – RS2

In this study, chlorite, gypsum, goethite, ilmenite, dolomite, magnetite, garnet, hornblende, kyanite, zircon and magnesianhornblende are identified only by the XRD from the soil samples. Although, feldspar group minerals such as orthoclase albite microcline also carbonate group of minerals like aragonite are identified in both FT-IR and XRD because it has the reason for the absence of the few minerals in XRD analysis, which are identified through FTIR, is due to the dis-orderedness (loss of crystalline nature) of the respective minerals. Table 3 represents the 2θ values, d-spacing, hkl (miller indices) and identified minerals in all the representative samples.

Table 3: XRD data and its mineral identification of red soil

Sample ID: RS1 Location: Na. Pudhoor				Sample ID: RS2 Location: Kattumalaiyanoor			
2theta	d-spacing	h k l	Minerals	2theta	d-spacing	h k l	Minerals
20.38	4.374	021	Chlorite	18.08	4.927	111	Magnesiohornblende
21.48	4.152	110	Goethite	20.38	4.374	021	Chlorite
26.14	3.414	041	Magnesiohornblende	23.35	3.817	130	Gypsum
27.50	3.243	040	Microcline	26.23	3.401	111	Aragonite
36.06	2.494	170	Hornblende	27.24	3.278	240	Hornblende
38.94	2.315	202	Chlorite	29.36	4.048	121	kyanite
39.78	2.270	332	Orthoclase	34.62	2.592	312	Microcline
41.90	2.156	134	Chlorite	36.06	2.494	170	Hornblende
45.21	2.006	107	Dolomite	42.07	2.151	152	Hornblende
49.70	1.834	107	Ilmenite	45.38	2.001	202	Albite
54.36	1.689	151	Chlorite	49.44	1.844	135	Chlorite
59.44	1.555	250	kyanite	54.10	1.695	311	Chlorite
67.74	1.384	335	Chlorite	59.44	1.555	250	kyanite
75.20	1.263	332	Aragonite	61.56	1.507	482	Magnesiohornblende
80.96	-	224	Aragonite	67.74	1.384	335	Chlorite
-	-	-	-	67.74	1.384	335	Chlorite
-	-	-	-	75.12	1.264	202	Goethite

V. CONCLUSION

The level of physic-chemical properties and minerals of Red soil samples are collected from the eight different locations on Thiruvannamalai district, Tamil Nadu have been determined. The FT-IR and XRD analysis of the Red soil samples indicates the presences of minerals such as Quartz and Clay minerals like Kaolinite and Montmorillonite are majorly present in the samples and also Feldspar minerals (Orthoclase, Microcline, and Albite) and Carbonate minerals (Aragonite and calcite) are present in the samples. Because of the dis-orderness (loss of crystalline nature) of the respective minerals, presence of some other minerals such as chlorite, gypsum, goethite, ilmenite, dolomite, magnetite, garnet, hornblende, kyanite, zircon and magnesiohornblende in soil samples which are identified only in XRD technique.

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